

The Study for Implementation of Simulation technique using C++ as a part of Operations Research

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Abstract:

In our presented study, we have tried to put the conclusion about the topics related to our study as operations research, simulation, and simulation programming languages. The use of operations research nowadays can be felt in every aspect of life like network scheduling, trafficking, transportation, military operations, and many more areas. Simulation being one of the techniques to optimize operations research problems and to formulate a system model becomes an important area of study. Various researchers have worked in the field of operations research, simulation, and simulation languages separately or as a combination of the two. But not too much attention has been paid to studying these areas altogether. Hence we will try to relate them all and present a conclusive study by doing research.

Keywords: *Operations Research, Simulation, Computer Simulation Languages, Random Variable, Random Variate, Probability Distribution Function, ForTran, GPSS, SPLs, etc.*

Introduction:

During the research work, we found that simulation is not only a part of operational research on the subject of mathematics but also related to Physics, Economics, Management-Sciences and with the advent of computer technologies it is being implemented in the form of many applications using the programming languages known as simulation programming languages (SPLs). Hence, when we found the topic of research to be an interdisciplinary topic, we opined to have a conclusive study in this field so that we may mark the aspects, projects and shortcomings of the research done earlier in this field and may come up with some suggestions that will certainly benefit the forthcoming researchers in this field.

We will present in this paper how simulation is being implemented using simulation programming languages by the use of computers to benefit the world and human beings.

Simulation as a part of Operations Research in the subject of Mathematics:

Operations Research has a vast range of computer-oriented applications these days as the approaches of Operations Research are applicable in business industries as well as the government sector or both. The areas where operations research applications are useful are – Accounting, Construction, Facilities Planning, Finance, Marketing, Manufacturing, Human Resources, and others. Simulation is one of the tools and approaches of Operations Research. Other tools and approaches in the subject of mathematics are – linear programming, integer programming, game theory, decision theory, dynamic programming, and others. The

mathematical model is required to describe the overall system when any of the above-stated techniques/ methods is used to simulate a problem.

Operations Research Development Phases

When we think about the processes or phases required in operations research development, it can be classified into the following six respective steps:

1. Take note for formulating the O. R. problem
Until the observation of the problem environment is not done, as the first step, we can not have proper information about how to formulate the problem. This phase includes the activities likely conferences, observations, site visits, and research.
2. Scanning and Defining the Concerns of the O. R. Problem
After observing the problem the second step that should be taken to formulate OR problem is defining and analyzing. We discover in this step the aims, possible inputs, and constraints that define the problem. Also, this results in the information about the actual requirement for a solution and its nature.
3. Creating a model
With the help of the mathematical model that must represent either hypothetical or real-world situations the third step of operations research is met. This mathematical model is comprised of variable definitions, equations, formulae, and linkages that describe the systems and the processes of the problem taken to formulate. Once the model is constructed it is put on the trial in the concerned field under various environmental conditions and then fine-tuned to make it work. In this prospect, the requirements of the management should also be considered.
4. Selection of accurate input data
The main focus of this step is to obtain a stream of data to test and run the mathematical model designed in the previous step. For testing and executing the mathematical model, the selection of accurate input data, a crucial phase of Operations Research Development; becomes compulsory. Some of the tasks related to this phase are External/ Internal data and fact analysis, opinion gathering, and utilization of computer data banks.
5. Furnishing a solution and its testing
Both the above phases of operations research development when completed accurately the solution to the problem can be reached. This solution may not appear as adaptable solution in some cases when it is tested with the created mathematical model but can be used to identify the other constraints affecting the solution of the problem in such cases. So to support current organizational objectives, it becomes necessary to make the adjustments and redesign the mathematical model.
6. Implementation of the obtained formulation of the problem
If everything happens to be correct and a proper solution has been obtained and tested successfully then resolving the issues of implementation authority, which is a behavioural issue to assure a quality of work and get the support of management, the solution is implemented in the concerned hypothetical or real work situation.

Discussion

There are two different approaches to performing all the above-mentioned phases of Operations Research Development, one is analytical and the other is logical. The benefit of a logical approach is that we can come up with a solution for the real-world system as it changes over time. Here we will find simulation as the best operation research technique for such problems. *Static* and *Dynamic* simulation models are the two types of simulation. The problems of a system at a particular point in time can be formulated using a *static simulation model* whereas on the other hand, the problems of a system that changes over time can be formulated using a *dynamic simulation model*. The problems with no random variable can be formulated using *deterministic simulation* and those that have one or more random variables can be formulated using *stochastic simulation*. Based on the model constructed to formulate a problem, the simulation can be classified into two categories, *discrete* and *continuous* model. When the decision variables vary only at discrete points of time, *discrete simulation* is applicable and when the decision variable changes randomly over time, *continuous simulation* is applicable. Using a simulation model to formulate problems in which the decision variable changes in discrete time intervals is known as a *discrete-event simulation*

model. The steps in a simulation study can be represented by using the above figure.

Random Variable Generation

The Probability distribution is helps represent Random Variables. The method of generating random variables from a set of given probability generation is known as *Monte Carlo Sampling* or *random variate generation*. The theory of such sampling is rooted in the interpretation of probability frequency and is entailed by a stable stream of random numbers.

Definition: A congruential method known as the linear congruential method with the following relation is used to generate random numbers:

$$x_{i+1} = (ax_i + c) \text{ modulo } m \quad (i = 0,1,2, \dots)$$

Proof: The above-represented linear congruential generator gives the remainder after performing the division of $(ax_i + c)$ by m and random numbers are thus generated by the relation

$$R_i = \frac{x_i}{m} \quad (i = 0,1,2, \dots) \quad (1)$$

The inverse transformation method requiring a cumulative frequency distribution in closed form can be used and the *algorithm* can be represented as:

Step 1: $f(x)$ is a given probability density function and for this cumulative distribution function is to be derived by using the relation

$$F(x) = \int_{-\infty}^x f(t)dt$$

Step 2: Random number r is now generated.

Step 3: Setting $F(x) = r$ solution is obtained for x . Hence obtained variable x is a random variate for a probability distribution function (pdf) given by $f(x)$.

Simulation Programming Languages:

Computer programming languages are important tools running on computers as application software to develop other required programs or software including operating systems, utilities, and other required application software. Writing the code to develop any program or software requires proper knowledge about the problem and/ or perspective for which the computer-oriented solution is going to be implemented. Writing the code for a complex simulation model is also a tedious and challenging task. For this very reason and to simplify the programming for simulation models, special computer-oriented languages known as computer simulation languages have been developed. ForTran, Basic, GPSS, GASP IV, and SLAM, as well as several others, are best-known simulation programming languages. Modern days programming languages that are part of academic education in several universities graduate level and post-graduate level degrees like C, C++, Java, Python, and several others that suits the management authority, are also being used to program simulation model.

Two different modeling approaches can be used according to the selection of computer simulation languages to program a simulation model. One such approach is the event-scheduling approach in which we have to identify the characteristic events to model the system and then write the required modules to describe the state changes occurring at the time of each event. Another approach is the process interaction approach in which we depend on the entity (or a customer) that necessarily undertakes going through the system to create the model of the system. ForTran, Basic, C, C++ and, Java like general purpose languages use an event scheduling approach and on the other hand process-interaction approach is used in GPSS. The system modeler while using SLAM can use either of the two approaches or even a mixture of the two that suits the model being analysed.

General-purpose programming languages provide greater flexibility and are widely used and available. On the other hand computer simulation, special-purpose languages offer a number of advantages. Most of the features required to program a simulation model and a natural framework are provided by the latter. For example, SLAM – special purpose simulation language, provides us the features to program simulation models as discrete event models, continuous models, network models, or any combination of these.

CPP Program to Generate Random Numbers:

Let us now develop a CPP program to generate random numbers using the relation (1) presented earlier,

Suppose x in the relation is represented in CPP language as an array of integers and is written as:

```
int x[] = { 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90, 100};
and m is 100.
```

i is the location or index of the element in x starting with 0 and ranging upto 9 ($i=0,1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9$)

The set of random numbers R_i that is also represented as an array in CPP language as:

```
int R[10];
```

is calculated by using the following CPP program:

```
#include<iostream.h>
#include<stdlib.h>
#include<time.h>
#include<conio.h>
void main()
{
int x[]={ 10,20,30,40,50,60,70,80,90,100}, m=100, R[10], i;
clrscr();
for(i=0;i<10;i++)
{
R[i]=random(x[i]%m);
cout<<R[i]<<"\t";
}
}
```

When the program is tested following output of above program is 10 random computer-generated numbers after execution as:

```
0    0    10    1    17    13    37    15    63    0
```

Also, if the content of array $x[]$ and the value of m is changed the random numbers during each time of the program execution gets changed.

Findings

The study done in this paper has been able to illustrate the processes or phases required in operations Research Development. For this, we have presented a relation to generate random numbers. Its algorithm and CPP program have also been presented in this paper. In the CPP program, we have taken care of all the steps of Operations Research Development and tested the program with different accurate data inputs. This CPP program is ready to be implemented either in hypothetical areas or in real-world systems. Thus we have also tried to summarize one technique related to simulation in the branch of Operations Research of the subject Mathematics and its implementation using the general purpose simulation programming language. The aim of study has been achieved.

Literature Review:

The study done in this paper is related to Operations Research, Simulation, and Simulation Languages. Many books, journals, and website pages have been studied and the content of the paper has been prepared leaving the statements or earlier research. The gist of all the above topics has been presented in this paper.

Conclusion:

Operations Research being a part of mathematics is also implemented in management to make appropriate decisions by optimizing the problem. Simulation is one of the techniques of optimizing the problem and creating models for the system that suit management authorities. Other techniques for Operations Research are analytical or more theoretical whereas simulation appears to be logical. Hence the implementation of a simulation model by using a computer becomes an easy task. For this special purpose simulation programming languages as well as general purpose programming languages can be used.

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